

Mix 11 ml of stock solution A and 5.5 ml of stock solutions B, C, and D, and dilute with water to total 5.5 liters of medium. The final concentrations are shown in Table 1. Because the pH value of this solution is higher than 7.0, adjust pH by blowing CO₂ gas directly from a CO₂ cylinder into the bicarbonate solution. The pH declines to 5.2 within 3-4 min. The pH value adjusted by CO₂ bubbling depends on the salt composition of the diluting water, but generally varies from pH 5.2 to 5.5.

The pH of this carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium rises no more

Table 1. Composition of salts and concentration of elements in bicarbonate solution.

Element	Concentration		Salt
	ppm	mM	
N	40	2.85	NH ₄ HCO ₃
P	8.72	0.28	Na ₂ HPO ₄
K	24.9	0.64	KHCO ₃
Ca	2.86	0.071	CaCl ₂ •2H ₂ O
Mg	3.61	0.149	MgSO ₄ •7H ₂ O
Fe	2	0.036	Fe-EDTA

than 0.2-0.3 unit/d, even at the vegetative growth stage of rice plants, and adjustment by CO₂ gas bubbling is necessary only every 3-4 d during

Table 2. Dry mass of rice shoots cultivated in carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium for 2 mo.

Treatment	pH	Dry mass (g)
Kasugai medium ^a	6.6	133 ± 14
Carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium	6.6	140 ± 8
Carbon dioxide-bicarbonate medium	5.5	132 ± 7

^aSources of N and K in Kasugai medium are ammonium sulfate and potassium chloride.

cultivation. Plant growth in this new medium was identical to that in the standard Kasugai medium (Table 2). □

Azolla growth relative to soil moisture

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Growth of azolla *A. pinnata*, Bangkok strain, was measured at different soil moisture levels. Five experimental treatments — 3-cm-deep water (control), saturated garden soil (with water film on the surface), moist garden soil, moist compost, and moist paddy soil — were used in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Polyethylene plastic sheets were laid beneath the soil in 1-m² plots to maintain the water level required in the 3-cm-deep and saturated treatments. Other plots were sprinkled as necessary. The experiment was kept in partial shade. Harvest was 20 d after stocking the azolla plants. The azolla crop was harvested by hand with most of the roots intact, washed to remove soil and other foreign matter, and

drained before the weight was recorded.

Fresh and sun-dried weights of 100 azolla plants from different growing media did not differ from each other (see table). Of the total biomass production, however, azolla grown on saturated garden soil, moist compost, and 3-cm-deep water had the highest fresh weight; plants grown on saturated garden soil recorded the

highest sun-dried weight. Azolla grown on saturated garden soil covered 98% of the experimental plot; that grown with 3-cm-deep water covered 95%. Dry weight percentage of harvested material did not vary among the treatments.

These results strongly suggest that azolla can be grown on saturated or moist media as productively as on water. □

Means^a of some growth components of azolla plants grown on different media, PSPC, Mambusao, Capiz, Philippines.

Growing medium	100-plant weight (g)		Computed plant weight (t/ha)		Dry weight (%)	Matting ^b (%)
	Fresh	Sun-dried	Fresh	Sun-dried		
3-cm-deep water (control)	11	0.6	8.9 ab	0.62 b	6.8	95
Saturated garden soil	9	0.8	11.6 a	0.96 a	8.3	98
Moist garden soil	12	0.8	4.9 c	0.33 c	6.1	50
Moist compost	12	0.8	8.3 abc	0.62 b	7.5	80
Moist paddy soil	13	0.8	5.4 bc	0.26 c	4.8	75
Test of significance	ns	ns	1%	1%	ns	—
CV (%)	18	21.2	30.1	30.26	10.1	—

^aAv of 4 replications. Means having a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level. ^bVisual observation.

Management of Zn deficiency in lowland rice

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We sought a practical and efficient method of curing Zn deficiency in the field.

IR6 was transplanted on high pH (8.2) clay loam soil with low organic matter (0.55%) and a cation exchange

capacity of 28 meq/ 100 g soil. Available DTPA-extractable Zn in the soil was 0.75 ppm. Fertilizer was 120-26-0 kg NPK/ ha. The lowest Zn deficiency symptoms and the highest yields were recorded in the treatments

Efficiency of source and method of Zn application for IR6.^a Tamboli (Sheikhupura), Pakistan.

Zn application method	Zn deficiency symptoms ^b 25 DT	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Efficiency of Zn application
Control (no Zn)	7	113.3 a	11.1 bc	5.63 c	—
Soaking the seed in 1% ZnSO ₄ solution for 24 h before seeding (0.25 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha)	4	113.6 a	12.5 ab	6.20 ab	2300.0
Dipping the sprouted seed in 1% ZnO suspension (0.25 kg ZnO/ha)	3	114.5 a	12.4 ab	6.28 ab	2628.0
Broadcasting ZnSO ₄ at 10 kg/ha on nursery bed before seeding (0.25 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha)	5	113.6 a	11.6 abc	5.89 abc	1056.0
Broadcasting Zn frit before transplanting at last puddling (0.25 kg/ha)	5	113.2 a	10.9 bc	5.81 bc	748.0
Broadcasting Zn frit mixture before transplanting at last puddling (0.25 kg/ha)	7	113.4 a	10.5 c	5.52 c	—
Dipping the nursery roots in 1% ZnO suspension	1	116.4 a	13.1 a	6.75 a	1119.0
Dipping the nursery roots in 1% ZnSO ₄ solution	1	116.4 a	13.1 a	6.74 a	1117.0
Broadcasting ZnSO ₄ at 10 DT (10 kg/ha)	2	115.0 a	12.7 ab	6.34 a	73.2

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other (DMRT). DT = days after transplanting. ^bSymptoms were recorded visually in a scale of 0-10: 0 = no deficiency, 10 = severe deficiency.

where nursery roots were dipped in ZnO suspension and ZnSO₄ (see table). Treatments affected productive tillers and yield significantly, but not plant height.

Dipping sprouted seed and nursery

roots in 1% ZnO suspension before seeding or transplanting was the most efficient method of curing Zn deficiency, followed by dipping sprouted seed and nursery roots in 1% ZnSO₄ solution and broadcasting 10

kg ZnSO₄/ha on the nursery bed before seeding. Broadcasting 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha 10 d after transplanting was least efficient. □

Biofertilizers for rice and their residual effect on rabi crops in Madhya Pradesh, India

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A field experiment was conducted to measure the response of rice to applications of fresh biofertilizers blue-green algae (BGA), *Azospirillum*, and *Azotobacter* and their residual effect on rabi crops. Soil was clay loam with 180-16-450 kg available N, P, and K/ha. Plot size was 8 m × 5 m in kharif, divided into 4 subplots of 5 m × 2 m for rabi crops.

Rice was transplanted on 16 Jul and harvested on 19 Oct 1984. Rabi crops were sown on 20 Nov and harvested 14 Mar–10 May 1985. Rice received 18 kg P and 10 kg K/ha. The table shows the treatments.

BGA was applied in 5-7 cm standing water 7 d after transplanting; growth

was sufficient to fix atmospheric N. Seedling roots were soaked 6 h in a solution of *Azospirillum* and *Azotobacter* before transplanting.

Rice yield was significantly higher with 10 kg BGA and the 2 N levels than in the control, but not with 15 and 20 kg BGA, showing erratic

response to inoculation (see table). Only chickpea responded significantly to residual fertility of biofertilizers.

However, all the treatment yields were significantly greater than that of the control. Residual effects of biofertilizers can be obtained in succeeding crops such as chickpea. □

Effect of BGA, *Azospirillum*, *Azotobacter*, and N on rice yield and residual effects on rabi crop yields. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)				
	1984 kharif rice (Ratna)	1984-85 rabi			
		Wheat (Lok-1)	Chickpea (JG62-404)	Linseed (R552)	Mustard (Varuna)
Control (no fertilizer)	3.2	1.0	1.5	0.3	1.0
10 kg BGA/ha	3.9	1.1	2.1	0.3	1.2
15 kg BGA/ha	3.2	1.0	1.9	0.4	1.0
20 kg BGA/ha	3.6	1.0	1.8	0.3	0.9
40 kg N/ha	4.1	1.0	1.9	0.3	1.0
60 kg N/ha	4.1	1.1	1.9	0.3	1.0
<i>Azospirillum</i>	3.5	0.9	1.9	0.4	1.0
<i>Azotobacter</i>	3.4	0.9	2.1	0.3	1.0
CD (0.05%)	0.5	ns	0.4	ns	ns

^aVarieties used are in parentheses.